

Analysis of interface ply angle effecting on stress distribution and ultimate strength of composite adhesive joints

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Keywords: Wind turbine blades, Composite adhesive joints, Thick adhesive layers, Fiber angle orientations, Finite element analysis

ABSTRACT

In this paper, a progressive damage model (PDM) is present for the ultimate strength analysis of single-lap composite adhesive joints. The predicting values are quite close to the experiment results which means the simulation approach is reliable. Based on the PDM analysis, a similar finite element analysis (FEA) is used to study the effects of fiber angles of Ply Adjacent to Adhesive Layer (PAAL) on the stress and strain distributions of adherends and adhesive layers. The results show that the fiber angle orientations of PAAL cause stress variations. The stress level of PAAL is the highest one with 0° fibers, while the strain and failure risk is the lowest; The stress level of PAAL is lowest with 90° fibers, while the strain and failure risk is highest; the stress and strain levels of PAAL with 45° fibers are between the results of 0° and 90°. At last, a common rule that how fiber angles of PAAL effect the strength and failure of the composite adhesive joints is achieved by comparing the simulation results and experiments data.

1 INTRODUCTION

Wind energy is a kind of clean energy and used on large-scale. Developing wind power has become the core content of many countries to promote energy structure transition and an important way to cope with climate change. The European Wind Energy Association (EWEA) predicts that the consumed wind energy will increase from 5.3% in 2010 to 15.7% by 2020. In China, the government makes a plan that the accumulated capacity will over 2100 GW till the end of year 2020 and wind power generating capacity will reach 420 billion KWH, which accounts for 6% of the total generating capacity [1] [2].

Due to the pursuit of efficient utilization of wind power, the length of the composite wind turbine blades keep on increasing, which is over 80m now. Connection problems are inevitable when composites are used in large structures. As key components of the wind turbine generator system, the blades bear tremendous wind and inertial load when transforming wind energy into mechanical energy. Therefore, all parts of the blades must be safe and reliable including the connection areas.

As one of the main means of connection, adhesive joints [3] [4] [5] [6] are widely used in wind turbine blades. For example, the suction surface and pressure surface, girder and web are bonded by adhesive, seen in **Fig.1**. Meanwhile, these parts are easy to do damage in the service period, seen in **Fig.2**.

Fig.1 The main adhesive regions in a wind turbine blade

Fig.2 Common adhesive failures in wind turbine blades a) grider and web bonding b) grider and web bonding c) trailing edge

Most of the researches of adhesive joints are concentrated on thin adhesive layers and cohesive zone models (CZMs) are used [7] [8] [9] [10]. However, in many practical applications, thin adhesive layers are usually not appropriate and hard to match the joint configuration. In the wind industry, the thickness of the adhesive layer may reach to 20mm. Thick adhesive layers [11] [12] reduce the requirement of dimensional precision of components which decreases the difficulty of manufacturing process.

This paper is focused on the influence of the fiber angle orientations of PAAL to the strength of the joint. All of the adhesive joints analyzed here are single-lap joints with Quasi-Isotropic Quasi-Homogeneous (QIQH) lay-ups to control the interface local effect.

2 EXPERIMENT

The lap plates used in the experiments were composite laminates made from SWANCOR 2511-1A /BS epoxy resin and unidirectional glass fiber through VARI process. The adhesive was WD3417-A /BS. The dimension of the joints prepared for testing is shown in **Fig.3**. Five groups of samples with different lap length were tested and the ultimate strength values are listed in **Table 1**.

Fig.3 The dimension of the single lap joints

Sample	t_c /mm	w /mm	l_1 /mm	t_a /mm
C1	2.25	25.4	12.7	2
C2	2.25	25.4	25.4	2
C3	2.25	25.4	38.1	2
C4	2.25	25.4	50.8	2
C5	2.25	25.4	63.5	2

Table 1: Lap length, width and thickness of the adherend and adhesive layers of the joints in the experiment

3 FINITE ELEMENT ANALYSIS

3.1 PROGRESSIVE DAMAGE MODEL

Unlike isotropic materials, the failure of composite materials is a progressive process. Generally, there are four parts in a PDM for composite materials, which are stress analysis model, failure criterion, stiffness degradation model and final failure evaluation method [13] [14] [15] [16].

3D model is established in finite element (FE) software ABAQUS (see in **Fig.4**) for the analysis. Hashin proposed a mode-related failure criterion and it is improved by Shokrieh with 7 failure modes. 3D Hashin's failure criterion is accepted here to describe the failure of the composite lap plate. Von Mises criterion is utilized to describe the failure of the adhesive layer as follows

$$\sqrt{\frac{1}{2}[(\sigma_2 - \sigma_1)^2 + (\sigma_3 - \sigma_1)^2 + (\sigma_1 - \sigma_2)^2 + 6(\tau_{23}^2 + \tau_{13}^2 + \tau_{12}^2)]} < \sigma_s \quad (1)$$

Where σ_s is the yield stress under uniaxial tension state. It is 25MPa here which is tested value by uniaxial tension test. The stiffness degradation model is shown in **Table 2**.

Fig.4 The finite element model

User subroutine USDFLD compiled by FORTRAN language is used to define the failure mode of the composite and the adhesive layer. Some parameters need in the simulation are listed in **Table 3** including stiffness and strength values of the composite, moreover, the elastic modulus and poisson's ratio of the adhesive are 3480MPa and 0.4 respectively. The end of the left lap plate in the finite element model (see in **Fig.4**) is fixed while a displacement load is applied in the end of the right plate. Once the reaction force decreases 30% or more, the whole single-lap joint is regarded as failure.

Failure mode	Degradation parameters
Fiber tension or fiber compression	$E_1' = 0.07E_1$
Matrix tension or matrix compression	$E_2' = 0.01E_2, G_{12}' = 0.2G_{12}, G_{23}' = 0.2G_{23}$
Tension or compression delamination	$E_3' = 0.01E_3, G_{12}' = 0.2G_{12}, G_{23}' = 0.2G_{23}$
Fiber-matrix shear	$G_{12}' = 0.4G_{12}$
adhesive	$E' = 0.001E$

Table 2: The stiffness degradation model

Property	E_1	E_2	E_3	G_{12}	G_{13}	G_{23}	ν_{12}	ν_{13}	ν_{23}
value	/GPa	/GPa	/GPa	/GPa	/GPa	/GPa			
	42	13	13	3.6	3.6	4.5	0.25	0.25	0.38
Property	X_T	X_C	Y_T	Y_C	Z_T	Z_C	S_{12}	S_{13}	S_{23}
value	/MPa	/MPa	/MPa	/MPa	/MPa	/MPa	/MPa	/MPa	/MPa
	850	500	67	170	67	170	115	115	95

Table 3: The stiffness and strength values of the laminate

Fig.5 shows an example of the PDM result and the experiment result. The simulation result shows the same failure area (the red area) as the experiment. All the experiment results and simulation results of the failure force are show in **Table x**. In the all five groups, the simulation results are quite close to the experiment values. Thus, the simulation approach used in here is valid for the analysis of single-lap joints.

Fig.5 Failure states of a single lap joint (C3) under tension load a) experiment result b) PDM result

sampl e	l_l /mm	Experiment/kN			PDM/kN	error (%)		
		AVG	min	max		AVG	min	max
C1	12.7	1.98	1.78	2.32	1.96	-1.0%	10.4%	-15.5%
C2	25.4	2.74	2.36	3.05	2.74	-0.1%	16.1%	-10.0%
C3	38.1	3.65	3.03	4.24	3.71	1.6%	22.2%	-12.5%
C4	50.8	4.80	4.52	5.30	4.74	-1.1%	5.1%	-10.5%
C5	63.5	5.46	4.70	6.26	5.77	5.5%	22.8%	-7.9%

Table 4: Experiment and PDM results of the ultimate strength of 5 joints

3.2 STRESS ANALYSIS OF FIBER ANGLE ORIENTATION OF PAAL

5 kinds of Quasi-Isotropic Quasi-Homogeneous (QIQH) lap plates with different lay-ups are used in the model and they have the same tensile modulus and flexible modulus to control the interface local effects. The stacking sequence and failure force of the joints are listed in **Table 5** (characters underlined are fiber orientations of PAAL). In this section, the FE model is the same as in PDM where the difference is we add a pressure load of 70MPa (equaling to 3360N applied at the end of the right plate) instead of the displacement load in order to compare the stress distributions of the joints under a same load level. The stress distribution results of the joints are shown in section 4.

Number	stacking sequence	Failure force/N
QIQH-1	<u>0</u> 45 90 -45 /90 -45 45 -45 /0 90 0 45 /0 45 -45 45 /90 0 90 -45 /90 -45 0 45	3459
QIQH-5	<u>-45</u> 0 90 45 /90 45 0 45 /-45 90 -45 0 /-45 0 45 0 /90 - 45 90 45 /90 45 -45 0	4024
QIQH-7	<u>90</u> -45 0 45 /0 45 -45 45 /90 0 90 -45 /90 -45 45 -45 /0 90 0 45 /0 45 90 -45	4220
QIQH-9	<u>-45</u> 45 0 90 /0 90 45 90 /-45 0 -45 45 /-45 45 90 45 /0 -45 0 90 /0 90 -45 45	4226
QIQH-11	<u>45</u> -45 90 0 /90 0 -45 0 /45 90 45 -45 /45 -45 0 -45 /90 45 90 0 /90 0 45 -45	4332

Table 5 Stack sequences and failure force of QIQH plates

4 RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Fig.6 shows the peel stress and shear stress distributions along a path on the surface of the adherend (line MN). The fiber angle orientations of PAAL of QIQH-1, 5,7,9,11 are $0^\circ, -45^\circ, 90^\circ, -45^\circ, 45^\circ$ respectively. The peel stress curves in **Fig.6(a)** are almost overlapped indicating that the fiber angle orientations of PAAL have little impact on the peel stress of the adherend when the lap plates have the same tensile and flexible modulus. While the shear stress shows a different circumstance. The shear stress increases with the fiber angle orientations of PAAL. Shear stresses along MN of 45° and 90° fiber angle of PAAL are 70% and 90% higher than that of 0° in stress concentration regions.

Fig.6 Stress distributions of PAAL along path MN a) Peel stress b) Shear stress

Fig.7 shows the tension stress σ_x and strain ε_x distributions along path MN. Due to different fiber orientations, there is an obvious difference among the tension stresses of line MN in the adherend. The tension stresses PAAL bearing decrease when the fiber angles increase. As a result, 0° PAAL sustains the highest tension stress but the tension strain of which is the minimum one. This phenomenon appears because of the different modulus in x direction of PAAL of every lap plate. Tension stress of 0° PAAL is 25~30 times and 3 times higher than those of 90° PAAL and 45° PAAL respectively in the stress concentration regions. Tension strains of 90° and 45° PAAL are 70% and 40% higher than that of 0° PAAL.

Fig.7 a) tension stress distributions along path MN b) tension strain distributions along path MN

Fig.8 shows the peel stress and shear stress distributions along a path on the surface of the adhesive layer (line MN). At the side of adhesive layer, the peel stresses also show little difference among different lay-ups. The shear stresses show a more severe uneven distribution, which means that the stress values in the middle area are smaller while the stress values on the edge of the adhesive layer are larger. The shear stress in the stress concentration regions of the adhesive layer adjacent to 0° lay-up is 11% and 7% higher than those of 90° lay-up and 45° lay-up.

Fig.8 Stress distributions on the surface of the adhesive layer along path MN a) Peel stress b) Shear stress

Aforementioned analysis indicates that the fiber angles of PAAL have influences on the stresses of the overlap region of a joint. We know that the damage initiation often appears in stress concentration regions. **Fig.9** is a diagram of how the fibers bear loads under peel stresses and tensile stresses with different orientations. The 0° layer has the same fiber orientation with the tension load, thus it has the highest load capacity. Meanwhile, it has the largest number of fibers to sustain the peel stress. Fibers in 90° layer are vertical to the tension load which means the transverse cracks are easily to appear and evolves under peel load. There is an angle between fibers of layers with fiber orientations between 0° and 90° and the direction of the tension load. Therefore the load bearing capacity is moderate.

Fig.9 Diagram of layers' load bearing capacity under tensile and peel stress with different fiber angles

5 CONCLUSIONS

The fiber angles of PAAL effect both the adhesive layer and the fiber layer. On the one hand, the load bearing capacity under peel stress and tension stress of the fiber layer decreases with the angles of fibers increase, which indicates that the layers are more easily to fail with higher fiber angles. On the other hand, the stress in the adhesive layer decreases with the angles of fibers increase, which reduces the risk of debonding. Thus, compared to 0° and 90° layers, 45° layer used in the joint may improve the failure strength of the adhesive joint in a certain extent.

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